

DELIVERABLE 3.6

Technical Progress Report

Development of the Visualisation Tool

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Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	PC	Project Coordinator
clCH	culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage	T[No.]	Task [No.]
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	UCD	User-Centred Design
EC	European Commission	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]
GA	Grant Agreement		

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
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Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

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Executive Summary

This technical report describes the progress made in developing the visualisation tools designed by BSC in consultation with FA. The tools reported here serve the broader aim set out in WP3's objectives: To build models of mediation between culinary tradition and modern living through historical recipes, connecting food traditions, food culture, storytelling, and education.

The two specific tools developed include: a **scrollytelling piece** to accompany FA's Living Recipes methodology; and an **embedding atlas** displaying similarity properties of the collected recipe dataset.

This report constitutes Deliverable 3.6 (D3.6) within Work Package 3 (WP3).

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

The present report describes the progress made in developing the visualisation tools designed by the team at BSC, in collaboration with the advisory team at FA. It constitutes **Deliverable 3.6** (D3.6) within Work Package 3 (WP3).

Under Task 3.4 (T3.4) – “Digitised EU recipe collections, IP issues and sustainability impact” (Months 3–18) – FA tasked BSC with preparing a progress report on the development and critical framework of the visualisation tool. The work also feeds into WP5, where, under T5.2, BSC will design and develop the interactive data visualisation on top of the datasets generated by the RELISH consortium.

The tools reported here serve the broader aim set out in WP3's objectives: to build models of mediation between culinary tradition and modern living through historical recipes, connecting food traditions, food culture, storytelling, and education. The meetings held with partners, and more closely with FA, over the course of this task informed the visualisations currently in development.

Following these guidelines, we will provide the consortium with two specific tools:

- The first, and our main contribution, is a **scrollytelling piece** that accompanies the **Living Recipes methodology** developed by FA (see **D3.4**)¹ for reading, reconstructing, and cooking recipes from historical culinary sources
- The second is an **embedding atlas** that displays the similarity properties of the whole collected recipe dataset (see **D3.3**)², foreseen for use as an assistance tool for researchers

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/21043975>

² Dataset report: <https://zenodo.org/records/19374402>

Full dataset: <https://zenodo.org/records/19328667>

1.1 Objectives

Our visualisation tools are built with the following objectives in mind:

1. Provide users within the consortium with assistive tools for their research into medieval recipe corpora (see **D3.3**)
2. Build a companion platform that follows FA's methodology for researching and exploring medieval recipes (see **D3.4**)
3. Guide non-expert users through the Living Recipes methodology and steps to reconstruct medieval recipes

Objectives 1 and 2 will give rise to independent visualisation tools. In particular, we will produce an **embedding atlas** showing hidden relationships between recipe texts that go beyond their geographical and temporal coincidences, together with visualisations that explore the “neighbourhood” of a specific recipe: a similarity radar plot and an ingredient co-occurrence graph. This focus on points of contact, similarity, and movement across time and space, follows directly from what the RELISH visualisation tool is meant to surface, as established in WP3 and carried into prototype work in WP5.

Objective 3, on the other hand, will be fulfilled through a **scrollytelling piece** – a digital storytelling technique that combines page scrolling with narrative (Figure 2). In keeping with the **user-centred design (UCD)** approach for BSC's visualisation work, the piece is built with its end users in mind: principally young adults, but also food-industry professionals, culinary researchers, and the general public. To guide users through the scrollytelling piece, we focus from here onwards on a real case study: the recovery of a medieval *escabetx* recipe from the *Llibre de Sent Soví*.³ This is an exercise FA carried out by applying their Living Recipes methodology and the methodology described here, which we later transformed into a tool under their guidance in order to recreate a dish from its original source text.

³ The *Llibre de Sent Soví* (1324, unknown author, Catalan) is the oldest known cooking manuscript in the European continent written in a language different from Latin.

2 Design

This section outlines the design process, considerations, and developments related to the scrollytelling piece and embedding atlas.

2.1 Feedback Loop

The development of the visualisation tools is guided by a feedback loop between the technical team at BSC and the advisory team at FA (WP3), the latter composed of anthropologists, historians, and professional chefs. Discussions take place during periodic meetings between the two groups, in which developments, doubts, and open questions are presented to FA, and their answers, guidance, advice, and corrections, are collected and fed back into the work.

At this stage, we have a validated prototype for one of the primary visualisations accompanying the scrollytelling, which will also serve as an assistant tool for experts. A second visualisation is currently being tailored in line with FA's collaboration.

2.2 Dataset

The visualisations described here are built on top of a curated dataset of recipes drawn from several medieval sources (**D3.3**). This dataset is the entry point for all the methods that follow: it comprises roughly 6,800 recipes in multiple languages, each translated into modern English by means of a large language model (LLM) and annotated with its entities – the ingredients, tools, and actions defined earlier – through an internally developed tagging pipeline. All data collection and pre-processing were carried out in-house using open-source tools.

2.3 The Embedding Atlas

As a first assistant tool, aimed at fulfilling Objectives 1 and 2 established above, we will provide the consortium with an **embedding atlas**: a 2D visualisation of the semantic relations between recipes.

We are performing a numerical embedding of each recipe text into a 768-dimensional vector space by means of a sentence transformer – a specialised natural language processing (NLP) model that maps meaningful sentences into numerical features that

can be analysed.⁴ Unlike a simple keyword search, which would only catch recipes that happen to share the same words, the sentence transformer encodes the *meaning* of the text: two recipes describing a similar preparation will land close together even if they were written in different languages, in different centuries, or with an entirely different vocabulary. Each of the 768 dimensions captures some latent aspect of this meaning, learned by the model from large amounts of text.

However, a key obstacle emerged: **it is impossible for humans to visualise a space of so many dimensions**. We therefore project the embeddings down to two dimensions using a Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction (UMAP)⁵ algorithm, which preserves the distances between vectors and therefore maintains the fundamental feature of the original embeddings.

In practice, UMAP tries to keep recipes that are neighbours in the 768-dimensional space as neighbours on the flat map, while pushing unrelated recipes apart, so that the local structure we care about survives the reduction. As a result, recipes that are far apart in the higher-dimensional space remain far apart in the low-dimensional one, and the same holds, conversely, for those that are proximate.

The resulting visualisation is an atlas — a two-dimensional map — of the semantic similarity between the recipes in our dataset, ideally covering the whole of Europe. Each point on the map stands for a single recipe, and its position is determined purely by the content of its text rather than by any label we assign in advance. A work-in-progress example can be seen in Figure 1.

Within the map, the user will observe a clustering of recipes that indicates their closeness regardless of origin, epoch, specific ingredient selection, or the particular wording of the recipe text. These groupings are not imposed by us: they emerge from the text itself. This means that the atlas can surface families or **neighbourhoods** of related dishes — shared techniques, common preparations, or lines of culinary influence — that would be hard to spot by reading the collection one recipe at a time. A researcher can use the map as an entry point, zooming into a dense cluster to inspect what its members have in common, or follow the gaps and bridges between clusters to trace how preparations travel and transform across regions and periods.

The atlas can therefore reveal hidden relationships among recipes that go beyond the obvious initial metadata, making it an efficient tool to support food researchers.

⁴ In particular, we use the model <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>.

⁵ <https://umap-learn.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 1: Embedding atlas of the medieval dataset. Each point is a recipe. Clusters are identified by their two most common ingredients.

2.4 Data-based Storytelling

Our primary contribution to the RELISH platform (see **D7.1** and **D7.2**⁶) is developing a storytelling piece in which the user takes on a similar role to a Living Recipes methodology participant (**D3.4**): throughout the exercise, they encounter a recipe they cannot yet cook (the information is incomplete, the context is missing, the instructions are ambiguous), and they are guided step by step through the process of testing and recreation. The specific format is called **scrollytelling**, because the main interaction from the user to drive the story is through scrolling, as you do with a long page website.

Secondary interactions (hovers, clicks) allow the user to obtain more detail on demand, preventing cognitive saturation and permit users with different levels of domain knowledge to control how much information they absorb. The other two visualisation

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/21044258>

tools in development – the similarity radar and the co-occurrence graph – will be built into this piece, but they will also be available as independent tools for researchers.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of a scrollytelling piece.

Throughout, the medieval *escabets* from the *Libre de Sent Soví* serves as the thread running through the entire experience. As the user moves down the page, interactive elements, animations, texts, and videos activate and change in sequence, creating an

immersive and progressive visual experience. A flow diagram of this process can be found in Figure 2.

More specifically, the scrollytelling tool designed by BSC follows the Living Recipes methodology described by FA for reconstructing a historical recipe. This unfolds in four stages, shown in Figures 3, 4, 5 and 7:

1. **Making a choice** – reading and interpreting the source text
2. **Theoretical cooking** – identifying its vital and complementary points
3. **Intuitive cooking** – testing, reviewing, and validating a first version of the recipe
4. **Interpretative cooking** – making intentional decisions to reach a final, parameterised version of the recipe

These four stages form the backbone of the scrollytelling design, marking the steps the user takes from the original source text to a cookable dish.

2.4.1 STAGE 1: Making a Choice

The user explores the narrative through a context search, supported by the first of our visualisations: a radial chart organised around a single recipe placed at its centre, as shown in Figure 2. The surrounding recipes are positioned along the radial axis according to their semantic similarity to that central recipe – the closer to the centre, the more similar they are.

Figure 3: Flow chart of Stage 1.

2.4.1.1 Semantic Similarity

Given two recipes, a semantic similarity score is computed in two steps:

1. We perform a numerical embedding of the recipe text into a 768-dimensional vector space using a sentence transformer, a specialised natural language processing (NLP) model.
2. We compute the cosine similarity between the two resulting vectors. Similar embeddings yield scores close to 1, while unrelated ones tend toward 0; in the visualisation, we map this onto a 0–100% scale.

The angular position of the recipes around the radar also encodes a similarity measure, but this time the measure is between the surrounding recipes themselves, rather than with respect to the centre. Once the recipes are chosen, they are arranged in an undirected graph whose edge weights are given by the Jaccard index between the entities that appear in each recipe pair. By “entities,” we mean *ingredients*, *tools*, and *actions*, previously identified and extracted from the recipe text using NLP methods (D3.3). Two recipes with identical sets of entities yield a Jaccard index of 1, while a value of 0 indicates recipes that share no elements.

Once the graph is built, we solve a travelling salesman problem to find the shortest tour that visits every recipe and returns to its starting point. This tour is projected onto a circle, which fixes the angular position of each recipe in the visualisation. In addition, the surrounding recipes are clustered using a K-means algorithm, highlighting families of similar recipes and revealing finer-grained relationships.

Finally, the size of each node encodes the complexity of the recipe. In our exploratory work, we consider two such metrics: centrality and sophistication.

Centrality

We define the centrality of a node as the normalised number of other nodes connected to it, so that a centrality of one means the node is connected to every other node in the graph. For the recipes at hand, we build a bipartite graph whose heterogeneous nodes are recipes, ingredients, and tools. Therefore, high centrality corresponds to those recipes drawing on a large number of distinct identified entities.

Sophistication

We borrow the notion of sophistication from economics and define a sophisticated recipe as one that uses ingredients – here we restrict ourselves to ingredients alone – of high complexity. Complex ingredients are, in turn, those that appear in sophisticated recipes but not in many recipes overall. The definition is circular, but it can nonetheless be resolved efficiently using standard numerical algorithms.

Users can filter the view by Top 10, Top 25, or Top 50 results and adjust the similarity range with a slider. Hovering over the central recipe reveals its connections to all surrounding recipes, with line weight proportional to similarity, while hovering over a cluster or an individual recipe highlights only its specific connections. A floating panel displays the recipe name, source, centrality/sophistication, and similarity score, and lets users switch between the full recipe text and a top-5 breakdown of its entities; when a cluster is selected, the same panel summarises its contents. A mockup of the radar visualisation, integrating all the elements discussed here, is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Radar visualisation mock design.

2.4.2 STAGE 2: Theoretical Cooking

The second stage of the methodology involves selecting the basic building blocks of a recipe. In our case, these are always the ingredients, tools, and actions, which we will collectively refer to as entities from now on. They can be drawn directly from the recipe text or, for the user working through the exercise, from the text tool in the radar visualisation. These will be further classified as **vital** or **complementary** points, and the user will also have the option to denote them as **optional** or **organoleptic** (including those connected to senses other than taste).

Figure 5: Flow chart of Stage 2.

2.4.3 STAGE 3: Intuitive Cooking

This is where cooks begin testing their abilities with the recipe under exploration. We already have all the information that can be extracted from the text, so the only method left is trial and error: the user, in the role of a cook, explores variations of the recipe and its building blocks.

Figure 6: Flow chart of Stage 3.

To this end, we provide a second visualisation: an undirected graph that displays co-occurrence relationships between ingredient pairs across the recipes. These

relationships are obtained by applying statistical methods to the entire set of ingredients, focusing on the normalised mutual information between pairs and retaining only those that are statistically significant relative to a degree-preserving null model with random connections. Once the relevant pairs are collected, we build the graph by adding the edges connecting them, each weighted by its mutual information value.

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The resulting visualisation is therefore a graph showing connections between ingredients that appear together in a statistically meaningful way, and these connections naturally give rise to clusters of co-occurring ingredient groups. With this information at hand, a user can decide to test variations on the recipe under study, always supported by evidence from reliable sources.

Figure 7: Schematic version of the ingredient co-occurrence graph.

To improve readability, the nodes are regrouped into broader categories: meat; fish and seafood; dairy and eggs; cereals and grains; legumes, nuts, and seeds; vegetables; beverages; oils and fats; fruits; and others. This reorganisation turns an initially dense, unlabelled graph into a navigable and interpretable tool, one that helps users investigate unresolved points in the recipe – seeing which ingredients, actions, or utensils tend to cluster together, and which combinations are statistically significant. A schematic of this graph is shown in Figure 7.

2.4.4 STAGE 4: Interpretative Cooking

Here, the user makes decisions about their own modern version of the reconstructed recipe. They do so as an informed choice, drawing on all the information accumulated in the previous stages.

At this point, our scrollytelling will feature real images from the reconstruction of the medieval *escabete*, carried out in collaboration with FA in 2025.

Figure 8: Flow chart of Stage 4.

3 Technology Stack

Here, we describe the technology stack used to develop the visualisation tools described above. In general, we will provide the RELISH platform with a Dockerised container which exposes the interactive visualisations but keeps any computation of processing of data under the hood, totally opaque to users. The whole structure is described below and summarised in Figure 8.

3.1 Backend Technologies

We label backend computations as those dedicated to data processing and analysis, without referring to specific details of the visualisations. We perform all of this in Python, using open-source tools and pretrained NLP models from Hugging Face (HF). For tasks involving large language models (LLMs), we use only open-source models deployed on the Mare Nostrum 5 infrastructure, owned by BSC.

Connection to the frontend, when needed, will be via a REST API and will be implemented using FastAPI in Python.

3.2 Frontend Technologies

3.2.1 Scrollytelling, Radar, and Graph Visualisations

For the scrollytelling part, we will build custom JavaScript code to render the entire visualisation on the user's side, using React as the framework. This has the advantage of allowing us to incorporate GPU acceleration when needed, which we foresee will be required for graph visualisation due to the large number of edges in a realistic case.

3.2.2 Embedding Atlas

To deploy the embedding atlas, we will realise a custom fork of Apple's Embedding Atlas, which is available as an open resource. Besides visualising the atlas, this resource also incorporates analysis modules, visualisation layers, as well as the possibility to perform a semantic search of the dataset, thus highlighting specific recipes in the map.

Figure 9: Diagram of the technological stack for the visualisation.

4 User Validation

Once the visualisation reaches its final stages, we will set aside a short period to test it with real users. This evaluation will follow an A/B testing approach: participants are divided into groups, each introduced to a slightly different version of the platform – varying, for instance, in layout, in how much information is revealed at each step of the scrollytelling, or in the way the radar and co-occurrence visualisations are navigated – and the responses of the groups are compared. Rather than asking users to judge a single design in the abstract, this lets us see which concrete variant works better, and why.

The test will combine quantitative and qualitative evidence:

- Behavioural signals such as how far users progress through the narrative, how long they spend on each stage, and how often they interact with the visualisations
- Users' own assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the version they received will be gathered through a short questionnaire

To keep the questionnaire findings representative of the platform's intended audience, we will aim to recruit participants from across its target user groups.

The results will feed directly back into the final design, letting us keep the choices that prove effective and revise those that do not. In this way, the test extends the UCD approach that guides the whole of this work.

5 Next Steps

This deliverable is submitted at M18, closing T3.4 and the WP3 data-collection and framing phase. Development of the tool itself continues under WP5, T5.2 – “Development and implementation of a prototype for recipe visualisation tool” (M13–M25) – already underway and which is the vehicle for the remaining work. The priorities carried into it are to: (i) finalise the ingredient co-occurrence graph with FA and integrate both supporting visualisations into the scrollytelling; (ii) complete the four narrative stages; (iii) run the user evaluation (A/B testing) and apply its findings, and (iv) scale the embedding and clustering pipeline from the current ~6,800-recipe set toward broader European coverage on BSC’s HPC resources.

The future schedule sits in WP5 and broken down as:

- **M18 (now, Jun 2026):** Submit D3.6; the curated dataset and pipeline feed the consortium’s sample data set (D5.2, due M21) and methodological framework (see D5.1)⁷
- **M19–M22 (Jul–Oct 2026):** Finalise and integrate the visualisations; carry out user testing and revisions
- **M22–M25 (Oct 2026–Jan 2027):** Implement the interactive prototype within T5.2, on top of the consortium’s data sets, through the close of the task at M25

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/20967900>

6 Ethics and IP

T3.4 explicitly covers IP and sustainability. Within RELISH, the substantive IP and sustainability assessment is led by FA and CITY, with support from UMIL, already explored in D3.3. Dedicated IP work will continue in WP4 through T4.5 that will result in D4.5. In WP6, an analysis of soft law instruments for ICH and food culture will take place for T6.3, which will result in D6.3. As a technical progress report, this deliverable addresses these dimensions only as they bear on BSC's data and tools, and defers legal analysis to those tasks.

6.1 Intellectual Property

The dataset draws on medieval sources whose original texts — such as the *Llibre de Sent Soví* — are in the public domain, though modern editions and translations may carry editorial copyright; the project therefore works from open, digitised collections and tracks each source's provenance. Under Article 16, the outputs BSC generates (translations, entity annotations, pipeline, and visualisation software) are owned by their producing beneficiary and subject to the consortium's access rights. Pre-processing used open-source tools, and outputs are intended for open release under the project's Data Management Plan (DMP).

6.2 Ethics and Data Protection

The work follows Articles 14 and 15 and the GDPR. The recipe corpus is historical and holds essentially no personal data. The main consideration is the planned user testing, which involves human participants and will be run under informed consent, with data minimisation, pseudonymisation, and secure storage.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable has reported, at the close of T3.4, the progress made by BSC in collaboration with FA on the RELISH visualisation tools. Two complementary tools have been developed: a scrollytelling app that guides users through FA's four-stage methodology for reconstructing a historical recipe – anchored in the medieval *escabetx* from the *Llibre de Sent Soví* – and an embedding atlas of the recipe collection, supported by the similarity radar and the ingredient co-occurrence graph, which serve both the narrative and independent research use. All of this is built on a curated, in-house dataset of roughly 6,800 recipes.

At submission, one of the main visualisations is validated as a prototype and a second is being tailored to FA's guidance, with the methodology and feedback loop between the two teams now well established. The work is therefore well positioned for its next phase: the design and implementation of the interactive data visualisation under WP5 (T5.2), where the dataset, pipeline, and validated prototypes developed here become the foundation for the consortium's recipe visualisation tool.